

Deliverable 7.1

Communication dissemination and exploitation plan (DEC)

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R	Document, Report	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
DEM	Demonstrator, Pilot, Prototype	<input type="checkbox"/>
DEC	Websites, Patent Fillings, Videos, etc	<input type="checkbox"/>
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc	<input type="checkbox"/>

Deliverables are additional outputs (e.g. information, special report, a technical diagram brochure, list, a software milestone or other building block of the action) that must be produced at a given moment during the action. A deliverable is an official report that provides enough information to the European Commission to ensure effective monitoring of the project.

The deadline is a statutory one, and we have to notify the project officer as soon as we know we are behind schedule, in the rarest situations where this is the case.

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Abstract

The present deliverable (D7.1) constitutes the FRUITDIV dissemination, communication and exploitation plan, due in M4. The deliverable aims to establish and outline a strategy for FRUITDIV's communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. Building on what was already agreed among partners in the drafting of the proposal, this document provides a further elaborated version and describes key tools, formats, channels and actions in detail, and indicates an action plan for activities to come.

WP7 has developed this deliverable and the WP7 leader (ARCADIA) has the main responsibility in leading and coordinating tasks related to communication and dissemination. However, these activities are largely depending on input from all consortium partners. Furthermore, GIS is the leader of Task 7.3 of WP7 that aims to implement training and capacity building and FEM is the leader of Task 7.6 related to project data management and open science. The deliverable describes the relevant roles and responsibilities and sets out the general principles of the project related to open science and data protection.

Table of content

Abstract	2
1 Introduction	4
2 Objectives related to communication, dissemination and exploitation of results	4
2.1 Objectives of WP7	4
2.2 Objectives of the plan.....	5
2.3 Distinction between communication, dissemination and exploitation	5
3 Communication and dissemination	7
3.1 Project identity	7
3.2 Audience and stakeholder mapping.....	9
3.3 Tools and channels	11
3.4 Format	15
4 Exploitation of results	20
4.1 Overall strategy	20
4.2 Exploitation routes	20
5 Plan of action and performance measures	21
5.1 Performance measures	21
5.2 Plan of action.....	22
5.3 Long-term sustainability and dissemination of projects results	23
6 Management of communication, dissemination and exploitation activities	23
6.1 Tasks and responsibilities	23
6.2 Editorial committee	24
7 Data protection and open science	25
7.1 Data protection.....	25
7.2 Open science	25
8 Conclusions	25

1 Introduction

This document includes the FRUITDIV project's **dissemination, communication and exploitation plan**. The Grant Agreement (GA) establishes two official deliverables for this plan (the present document: D7.1 due M4, and an updated version: D7.5 due M48). In addition to these two deliverables, it may happen that changes or updates are introduced to the plan throughout the project's lifetime (e.g. components such as stakeholder mapping, action plan or our internal checklist may be updated and enriched). Such changes will be included in routine reporting.

The chapters of the present deliverable are listed as follows:

Chapter 2: Objectives related to communication, dissemination, and exploitation of results, briefly outlines the main objectives related to the tasks of WP7 and to the communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities. Furthermore, the chapter sets out to distinguish between communication, dissemination, and exploitation in the context of Horizon Europe (HE) research projects.

Chapter 3: Communication and dissemination, presents the first key part of the plan, providing an overview of how communication and dissemination main activities will be articulated based on the targeted audience on one hand, and a general audience on the other hand. Tools, channels, and formats to be used are described.

Chapter 4: Exploitation of project results, is the second key part of the plan, focusing on exploitation activities aiming to make concrete use of the project's results.

Chapter 5: Plan of action and performance measures, outlines the various activities, the work packages involved, target audiences as well as performance measures applied.

Chapter 6: Management of communication, dissemination and exploitation activities, refers to the different responsibilities of partners involved in these activities and the crucial role of the WP7 leader as a coordinator.

Chapter 7: Data protection and open science, sets out an overview regarding the FRUITDIV project's approach in the context of data protection, communication, and open science principles.

2 Objectives related to communication, dissemination, and exploitation of results.

The below sections outline the objectives of WP5, as well as the objectives of the dissemination, communication and exploitation plan. Furthermore, the similarities and distinctions of the three different concepts (dissemination, communication and exploitation) are explained.

2.1 Objectives of WP7

The EU-funded DETECTIVE project will monitor, characterise, use, and conserve the diversity of emblematic fruit tree crop wild relatives (CWR), with a particular emphasis on Malus, Pyrus, and Prunus. In addition to breeding programmes, FRUITDIV will work with networks of farmers and associations to help characterise CWR progenies in various pedo-climatic conditions in Europe. Overall, the FRUITDIV multi-actor approach involving geneticists, forestry officers, germplasm

curators, farmers and citizens will foster the in situ and ex situ conservation of CWR and promote sustainable agricultural practices across Europe.

Within FRUITDIV, the overall objective of WP7 is to ensure dissemination and optimal uptake of FRUITDIV results. This will be done through a series of dedicated tools and sharing of information with all concerned actors (from breeders to the general public) identified through a detailed mapping. Furthermore, WP7 will support communication and dissemination activities and facilitate knowledge transfer and cross-pollination. Eventually, WP7 will work to ensure a successful combination of stakeholder engagement (input) with a dedicated communication and dissemination strategy (output) to fully exploit the results of the research.

2.2 Objectives of the plan

Communication, dissemination and exploitation activities are key to achieve the overall goals of the FRUITDIV project and to maximise its impact. The present plan sets out a structured and systematic approach to plan, coordinate, monitor and assess all impact-related dissemination, communication and exploitation activities. In this framework, WP7 will coordinate project-wide activities and implement dissemination and exploitation measures to ensure that results meet real needs leading to a strong uptake. As noted, some components of the plan will be regularly reviewed and updated as necessary throughout the project lifetime, and a second version of the plan will be submitted in M48.

2.3 Distinction between communication, dissemination and exploitation

Communication, dissemination and exploitation are all part of any HE project's legal obligations of the GA. While closely related, these three concepts differ from each other, and it seems important to briefly outline the differences for the purpose of this document:¹

- **Communication** relates to the promotion of activities and results of the project and aims to reach out to a wide range of audiences including citizens, media and different stakeholder groups. These activities take place from the start of the project until the end and aim to engage with specific stakeholders and experts of the field, but also to raise awareness, and be transparent, among the general public about the project activities and objectives, how public money is spent, and benefits of European collaborations. Communication activities include using various media channels to convey clear messages about the project. It should be noted that boundaries between communication and dissemination activities are sometimes blurred.
- **Dissemination** implies making the project results public and, through open science, disseminating knowledge and results for others to use (free of charge). The target audience is made up of different groups that may take an interest in the potential use of the results. Other scientists constitute a key target for these activities, however, also other stakeholder groups that can learn from the results can be important, including authorities, policy makers, food supply chain actors and civil society. Dissemination activities take place as soon as the project has any results to share, and may include publication of results on scientific magazines, scientific or targeted conferences, or databases. The aim of these activities is to boost the

¹ European Commission website, Horizon Europe, <https://rea.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-11/Communication%2C%20Dissemination%20and%20%20Exploitation-2021.pdf>

impact of the project, allow other researchers to benefit and build on the available results, contribute to the advancement of the state of the art in the field, and make scientific results a common good. As mentioned, boundaries between communication and dissemination activities are sometimes blurred. Therefore, these two activities are presented under one chapter in this document (see Chapter 3).

- **Exploitation** refers to making concrete use of results, be it for commercial, societal, environmental, or political purposes. The target audience for these activities include researchers, industry and SMEs, as well as relevant stakeholder groups such as authorities, policy makers, civil society, and others. Exploitation activities come towards the end of the project, when exploitable results become available, and go beyond the end of the project period. Activities include creating roadmaps to uptake, prototypes, software, as well as sharing knowledge, skills and data obtained through the project. Outputs may include contributing to new legislation or policy recommendations. The aim of exploitation is to support innovation, the economy and society, as well as addressing a specific problem or responding to an existing demand.

FRUITDIV aims to start mainly with communication activities, add the dissemination activities as results progress over the project lifetime, and then gradually increase both communication and dissemination activities. Exploitation activities on the other hand start at a later stage.

The figure below demonstrates these three streams and example activities that may be part of them.

Figure 1: Overview of communication, dissemination and exploitation streams

3 Communication and dissemination

The overall objective of communication and dissemination activities is firstly to promote the project and ensure its visibility. All the envisaged activities are focused, either directly or indirectly, towards the achievement of this objective. Promoting the project is crucial as it is a way of demonstrating how European research projects contribute to the knowledge diffusion across the international scientific community, and accounting for public spending by providing tangible evidence of the project's added value and benefits to society. Furthermore, communication and dissemination activities help to enable replicability and further use of the project results.

The below sections outline some of the key activities that set a crucial foundation for communication and dissemination, namely an established project identity, a thorough stakeholder mapping, main tools, channels and formats to be used throughout the project.

3.1 Project identity

Communication activities begin with the creation of the project's identity and public image to enable a wider engagement throughout the project.

Logo

The FRUITDIV project logo consists of a green leaf symbol followed by the full project name. The font used is welcome 2019. The below images show the logo in its original colour (to the left) as well as a black and green version (to the right). Fruits species under research in FRUITDIV are completing the logo

Figure 2: FRUITDIV logo

Fruit species

Colours

The colours of the logo and the project identity are presented below.

Figure 3: FRUITDIV colours and project identity

Templates

Templates aligned with the FRUITDIV project identity have been developed. The Word template to be used for the project deliverables is included in the present document). Furthermore, the PowerPoint template to be used by project partners for presentations, is presented here below.

It can be noted that the fonts mainly used in the templates are TW Cen MT (for headings) and Calibri (for text).

Figure 4: FRUITDIV PowerPoint template (first page)

3.2 Audience and stakeholder mapping

The dissemination of knowledge from FRUITDIV will be greatly facilitated by the multi-actor approach adopted in this project. A multi-step and multi-channel stakeholder engagement strategy has been designed to maximise the impact of engagement and dissemination activities, carefully tailoring materials and tools to the specific needs of the target audiences. Stakeholder activities will include both input (e.g. creation) and output activities (e.g. dissemination).

There are two levels of audience and stakeholder mapping. The first one relates to the establishment of the networks that will be associated to FRUITDIV activities, while the second one is a wider stakeholder mapping covering also other actors, areas and countries, establishing a Stakeholder Platform. The two levels of audience and stakeholder mapping are further described below.

Through a multi-actor approach, FRUITDIV will bring together a diversity of actors based on their knowledge, expertise and role in the society, for participating to the research as well as for promoting and facilitating the use of project results.

FRUITDIV findings and results will be packaged to reach, engage and address end-user needs and will be widely shared with all relevant actors. Resources will be mobilised to ensure that the project remains visible to society and that results are disseminated to all relevant targets outside of the consortium.

A Stakeholder Platform (SHP), and extensive list of contacts, has been initiated for this purpose. The SHP consists in a list of contacts, that will be enlarged and completed as the project progresses, managed by the WP7 leader (ARCADIA), which will be used to disseminate information and invite relevant actors and the general public to events organised by FRUITDIV and to keep them informed about the project's progress, activities and results. For example, the stakeholders included in this list will receive the project newsletter, informative e-mails and updates on a regular basis.

To establish the SHP, a wider mapping will take place to identify as many relevant stakeholders and targets as possible in view of disseminating the results of the project as widely as possible. This mapping will include academic stakeholders, advisory services, technical institutes, regulatory bodies, farmer's union, but also media and the general public. The mapping activity is currently on-going and consists in the following steps:

1. **WP7 establishes main and sub-categories of the stakeholder mapping**, based on the target groups outlined below, and circulates these categories in an excel document to consortium partners for input and validation. On national level the mapping has taken place for the stakeholders. A complementary mapping is performed at the EU level with all other stakeholders not directly involved in the FRUITDIV activities that take place at the national level.
2. **Once input from all partners has been received, the stakeholder categories are finalised by WP7.** Another round of consultations with all partners takes place, this time to identify stakeholders for the various categories at regional, national and EU level. At this point, partners are asked to focus on their countries/regions of expertise.
3. **WP7 finalises the mapping based on the input from partners.** As the listing will include names and contact details to stakeholders, the first priority will be to reach out to all stakeholders to inform them about FRUITDIV and that they have been listed as potentially relevant stakeholders in the context of the project. The stakeholders will then be provided with the choice of opting out or remaining included in this listing. The FRUITDIV project ensures that personal data processing and management comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) provisions.
4. **The listing implies that stakeholders receive updates about the project activities and results such as events, newsletters or other communications**, and that they may also be contacted to participate in specific actions on a voluntary basis. Stakeholders are informed that they may opt out from the list at any point throughout the project lifetime.
5. **The final list will be kept on the project's internal SharePoint to** enable consortium partners to update the list and add any other stakeholders throughout the project period. As this list will be a dynamic document, a regular monitoring carried out by WP7 will be in place in order to keep track of new additions and inform them about the listing and provide them with the option of being included in the list or not.

While a thorough mapping of stakeholders and targets at an early stage of the project is crucial in order to initiate communication activities, it is important to note that additional stakeholders may be identified throughout the project. WP7 will collect information from partners to enrich the listing and identify targets with the aim of further developing the dissemination plan and ensure a wide outreach of communication and dissemination activities.

The consortium has already identified a significant initial list of actors covering CWR and fruit tree breeding in the EU to ensure this approach. Such identification has been facilitated by the previous projects carried out by consortium partners. This has secured the identification of more than 400 European and national stakeholders having expertise and competences in CWR that will be added to our stakeholder database dissemination and communication materials and tools will be directed to

them in a tailored way and/or simultaneously to groups sharing the same interests. Relevant actors are grouped as follows:

Table 1: Key actors for communication and dissemination activities

Target groups	Role in the project
TG1: The scientific Community including CWR specialists	Scientists will be contacted to fine-tune project approaches. Dedicated attention will be devoted to liaising with projects on the same topics. Researchers will be invited as multipliers to disseminate project’s results after the end of the project.
TG2: Breeders	They will have a concrete view of the project outcomes at local/regional levels under real operational conditions. Project findings will be presented for adoption of new CWR-derived material for breeding purposes in Europe and other countries.
TG3: Farmers and/or their representatives and advisors	They will be associated to communication and dissemination activities to demonstrate to them that novel varieties with improved traits based on CWR are possible. Interactions with this group of stakeholders will help implementing FRUITDIV results at local and regional levels. Advisors will act as multipliers even after the closure of the project.
TG4: Foresters, forestry agencies and associations of regional and national parks	These groups are key players in the implementation of sustainable conservation plans. In the context of FRUITDIV, this group will have the role to boost the added value of fruit tree CWR at the same level as forest trees.
TG5: Agro-food supply actors	This group of actors, from processors to retailers, is not directly involved in the management of CWR nor in the breeding of new phenotypes but contributes to the awareness raising of such research. They can promote the added value of CWR in breeding processes down to consumers.
TG6: Society and consumers	They are key targets since a major objective of FRUITDIV is to improve public acceptance of products derived from new varieties using CWR traits. We will raise public awareness of the sector challenges and availability of new CWR-derived material. Furthermore, they can be considered key actors in the conservation of biodiversity, fruit tree CWR included.
TG7: Policymakers and public bodies	This group includes bodies at regional, national and EU levels. They will be engaged in the dissemination of FRUITDIV results and in stakeholder’s discussions to issue policy recommendations. The group will be established in the very early days of the project to bridge research to policy in a concrete manner.

3.3 Tools and channels

The below sections provide an overview of the main tools and channels to be used for communication and dissemination activities in the FRUITDIV project.

Website

The website will contribute to the communication and dissemination objectives of informing and raising awareness among target audiences and disseminating results. It is the core public communication channel of the project as it enables all stakeholders and the general public to follow the development of the project.

The FRUITDIV website domain has been registered as: www.fruitdiv.eu and will be launched May 2024.

The website will consist in both static pages that will stay the same, and dynamic pages that will be updated regularly during the project period, including with videos, pictures, informative texts, public tools and deliverables when available. Information targeted to both stakeholders specialised in the field and to the general public will be published on the website and all content will be accessible to viewers without restriction. Furthermore, the website will enable visitors to sign up to newsletter and information send-outs, as well as to get in contact with the project partners in case of questions.

Figure 5: Website (example page)

Regarding the structure of the website, the “Home page” briefly introduces the project and provides hyperlinks to other key pages of the website through a menu that is placed at the top of the page, such as project information, publications, latest news etc. From this page, you can also use a search function as well as access the social media pages of FRUITDIV through links/symbols provided. Furthermore, it is possible to subscribe to the project newsletter at the bottom right of the home page.

When clicking on “The Project” in the menu, a sub-menu listing project summary, goals and objectives, work packages, partners, and links, becomes visible. These pages are briefly described below:

- **Project summary:** this page provides a full summary of the SUPPORT project, its motivations, objectives and main activities.
- **Goals and objectives:** this page further outlines the specific objectives of the project and its ambitions for the project period.
- **Work packages:** here, the 6 work packages are described, including the main objectives and activities of each WP.

- **Partners:** here, the logos of each of the consortium partners are presented. When placing the mouse over one logo, information about the organisation and a link to the organisation's website become visible.
- **Links:** this page provides links to other projects and initiatives that are relevant or related to the objectives and activities of SUPPORT. This page will be updated regularly during the project period.

The other pages listed in the menu include the following:

- **Publications:** this page will present the material resulting from the research activities of the project excluding confidential information. The page will be constantly updated with new material throughout the project, including formal documentation, scientific publications, articles, pictures, etc.
- **Medias:** the media pages provide access to all material produced with the purpose of project communication and dissemination. Several sections are listed under media through a sub-menu including in the press, newsletters, communication toolkit, photo galleries and videos. These pages will be regularly updated throughout the project.
- **Events:** information about upcoming events is available on this page, presenting key information regarding events relevant to the field and that may be of interest to FRUITDIV partners and stakeholders, as well as events related to the project activities (e.g. workshops, trainings, conferences). This page will be regularly updated throughout the project.
- **News:** the news page includes any relevant news related to the project. This may include reports from recent events, information about upcoming events, publication of a newsletter or a new communication tool, or results from research activities. This page will be regularly updated throughout the project. In addition, "activities of the month" following different themes relevant to the project will be posted here. News posts will also be shared in social media through LinkedIn and Twitter in particular.
- **Contact:** a contact form is available on the "Contact" page in case the website visitor would like to get in contact with the project coordination team. It will require the website visitor to enter personal data in order to submit a message to the FRUITDIV project.

The website will be developed in WordPress, which will enable easy content management during the project and upon its completion.

The website is developed and maintained by ARCADIA based on input and feedback from all consortium partners, and in particular the project coordinator.

In addition to the official project website, INRAE has set up an internal channel for the consortium partners. It is the internal communication system of the project to enable exchange and communication within the consortium, share relevant information such as confidential deliverables, raw project results, etc., modify documents and disseminate results within the project.

Social media

FRUITDIV will have a social media presence on Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn and YouTube. The activities on social media will expand the outreach of the project, thus enabling communication of the project

results to specific target groups and also encouraging responses and questions from these groups. The profiles have been set up and will be launched together with the website in Mid-June 2023.

Social media is a key component of any promotional effort. As soon as the social media profiles have been launched, all partners will be invited to follow them, and also to retweet and resend messages that are published. Active participation by partners in these channels will be important, including posting news, updates and relevant information with tags/labels to FRUITDIV, but also retweeting and commenting on partners' and other stakeholders' comments and relevant messages related to the topics of FRUITDIV. Another important factor regarding the social media activities will be to broadly use the trending hashtags linked with the topics addressed by the project. Posts and updates made by the consortium partners may be either in English or in their national languages (together with an English translation).

The activities on social media will be maintained throughout the duration of the project and will provide project gains with good visibility in relevant LinkedIn groups and on Twitter. Regular posts will be produced to keep online communities interested and informed about FRUITDIV activities, including public deliverables, scientific publications, details and news about trainings or events organised in the context of the project, as well as other relevant facts worth bringing up to attract the targeted online community's attention. YouTube will be used to enable the target audience to access video content related to the project and its activities. Once published on YouTube, videos will be embedded to the official FRUITDIV website and will also be shared on the other social media accounts.

ARCADIA is in charge of the core activities on social media, including creating the profiles and posting regular content based on input from other partners, as well as following existing relevant social media channels and groups. Consortium partners are encouraged to contribute by following the FRUITDIV profiles on Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube, as well as using the possibility to retweet and repost content from their organisations' channels using relevant hashtags.

YouTube: [@FRUITDIV_HE](#)

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/fruitdiv/>

Twitter: [FRUITDIV \(@FRUITDIV\) / X \(twitter.com\)](#)

Media relations

All partners will contribute to the project communication by sharing the materials and tools developed for this purpose with press contacts of their own regions and countries. The work package leader for WP7 (ARCADIA) will coordinate the partners in relation to when they should get in touch with press contacts and will provide partners with the written and audio-visual material, which the partners may need to translate and adapt according to their needs.

Exchange with other projects

FRUITDIV will actively engage with projects on related initiatives (national and international R&I activities), specifically ongoing H2020 and HE projects. A dedicated task (see Task 7.4) is fully dedicated to interaction with such other projects. To ensure synergy and collaboration between projects where possible, FRUITDIV proposes to prepare back-to-back project meetings, organise joint activities, workshops and common communication and dissemination activities.

Events

Different types of events make up an important channel for communication and dissemination. A sample of events that will be organised within the framework of FRUITDIV is listed below.

- Main scientific findings and results of the project will be presented in **international meetings and congresses** with the aim to reach out to the scientific communities. In such events, specific sessions may be coordinated to increase the project's visibility. Some examples in the first phase of the project include the following:
 - ISHS Plum and Apricot Symposium, 22-26 April 2024: Presentation of FRUITDIV and experimental plots involved in the project.
 - IUFRO 24-29 June 2024: Presentation of FRUITDIV in the session on international collaborative networks.
- **Scientific workshops** will be organised, securing interdisciplinary research at the EU and international level.
- **Conferences for actors at national level** will be organised in national languages in order to communicate and transfer FRUITDIV results to national and regional actors. Such events will include interactions with citizens and consumers.
- **Project workshops and events** will be organised to disseminate and exploit results for mutual learning and understanding (e.g. multi-actor workshops and capacity building workshops as foreseen under Task 7.3).
- **AGRI exhibitions and trade fairs** will be attended by FRUITDIV partners to disseminate results and outputs.
- **Consortium networks** will be used for communication of project results and outcomes in specific events.
- **A final conference** will be organised at the end of the project to present all project results.

3.4 Format

The main formats used for the communication and dissemination activities of FRUITDIV are outlined in the sections below, including printed communication tools, practice abstracts, newsletters, scientific publications and others.

Printed communication tools

A communication toolkit will be developed, containing a leaflet, a poster and a concept note. The **leaflet/flyer** has the purpose of briefly presenting FRUITDIV in an accessible way through both text and visuals, that may attract both the general audience and a more targeted audience. In a similar style, a **poster** is developed which may be used to present the project at events and conferences, providing an overview of the project highlighting key information. The **concept note** is aimed at the targeted audience with previous knowledge of the subject and outlines the key objectives and activities of the project, as well as the expected results and impacts. It can for example be used to introduce the project to stakeholders. All the communication tools will be made available through the project's website and the INRAE intranet and may be printed and distributed at relevant events. Other printed material and tools might be developed during the project lifetime as needed, for example

general presentations of the project, policy briefs, factsheets for farmers or specific material to be used at the occasion of the final conference.

In addition to the printed communication tools, FRUITDIV will also produce **informative videos** that will be posted both on the website and on social media.

The poster

Objectives and activities

FruitDiv is a Horizon Europe research project launched on the 1st of January 2024. FruitDiv aims to monitor, characterise, use, and conserve the diversity of fruit tree Crop Wild Relatives (CWR), with a particular emphasis on pome (Malus, Pyrus) and stone (Prunus) fruits.

CWR are wild plant species closely related to cultivated crops. They hold important potential as a source of genetic diversity, offering agronomic and nutritional traits like pest and disease resistance, tolerance to drought, and adaptability to fluctuating climatic conditions affecting fruit quality and production. Harnessing this genetic diversity is crucial

for enhancing crop improvement, ensuring sustainable agricultural practices, tackling climate challenges and meeting the demands of food security and better nutrition.

This approach aligns with the goals of the European Green Deal, and the Biodiversity and Farm to Fork strategies, aiming i.a. to

reduce pesticide use and risks. Moreover, fruit trees' long lifespan and a current production dominated by only few cultivars make fruit trees particularly vulnerable to the effects of global changes. Further research and conservation efforts are thus needed to unlock the full potential of fruit tree CWRs and secure our agricultural future.

Expected results and impacts

- **A species-wide inventory of fruit tree CWR diversity**, improving the situation for pome and stone fruit CWR at the European level and balancing their representativeness in national and European PGR programmes to enhance their characterisation, and a better conservation and use.
- **An improved characterisation of CWR diversity that relies on the most innovative technologies**, organising European-wide CWR collections planted in multi-sites and interconnected so as to share genetic and phenotypic characterisation of CWR behaviours in multiple environments and under complementary cultivation regimes using innovative methodologies. Also, the potential interest of long-term maintenance of the same plant material in different agronomic and pedo-climatic conditions across Europe will be addressed and in the medium-term rationalised conservation strategies, both ex-situ and in-situ, will be proposed for future uses.
- **A greater insight into the characteristics and the value of fruit tree CWR**, through the development of an innovative strategy relying on germplasm characterisation and implementation of up-to-date methodologies of pangenomic-assisted breeding, graph-based integration of heterogeneous data including biochemical process knowledge and CRW-adapted genomic/metabolomic prediction models. Furthermore, state of the art genomic and phenomic approaches currently under development in major annual crops to fruit tree breeding will be used to drive the sustainable conservation and use of CWR genetic resources.

The 1 page summary/concept note

FruitDiv is a European research project launched on the 1st of January 2024. The project is funded under the Horizon Europe framework for a period of five years (January 2024-December 2028). FruitDiv aims to monitor, characterise, use, and conserve the diversity of fruit tree Crop Wild Relatives, with a particular emphasis on pome (*Malus*, *Pyrus*) and stone (*Prunus*) fruits.

Crop Wild Relatives (CWR) are wild plant species closely related to cultivated crops. They hold important potential as a source of genetic diversity, offering agronomic and nutritional traits like pest and disease resistance, tolerance to drought, and adaptability to fluctuating climatic conditions affecting fruit quality and production. Harnessing this genetic diversity is crucial for enhancing crop improvement, ensuring sustainable agricultural practices, tackling climate challenges and meeting the demands of food security and better nutrition.

This approach aligns with the goals of the European Green Deal, and the Biodiversity and F2F strategies, aiming to reduce pesticide use. Moreover, fruit trees' long lifespan and a current production dominated by only few cultivars make them particularly vulnerable to the effects of global changes. Further research and conservation efforts are thus needed to unlock the full potential of fruit tree CWRs and secure our agricultural future.

IN THIS CONTEXT, THE FRUITDIV PROJECT AIMS TO:

- Monitor CWR in the European genebanks among the European historical hotspots of diversity;
- Characterise genetically CWR to establish ex situ collections representative of the CWR diversity to be further multiplied in common gardens, and to identify key CWR natural populations to be preserved in situ;
- Share and develop new and high-throughput phenotyping tools and protocols for the evaluation of traits linked to resistance to pests and diseases, and adaptation to low-input cultivation systems in highly contrasted environments;
- Integrate CWRs in plant genetic resources collections and breeding programs by developing new methods for wild-to-crop translational research;
- Promote sustainable data sharing by standardising and giving access to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) genotypic and phenotypic Open Data;
- Develop pre-breeding material and CWR-adapted methodologies for breeding at single and multi-trait scales, making use of existing or future multi-site experimental designs and predictive models;
- Foster a more efficient and sustainable conservation of CWR, in situ, on-farm and through NGOs, and enhance stakeholders' awareness of the value and importance of CWR; and
- Promote the use of CWR or first-generation pre-breeding material by breeders to disseminate plant material of interest for growers, organic farmers and the fruit tree industry.

The FruitDiv consortium is coordinated by INRAE (France) and includes 27 multi-disciplinary partners from 10 EU Member States and four other European countries. ■ CONTACT: Véronique Decroocq, Project coordinator, veronique.decroocq@inrae.fr

The four-page leaflet

Exploiting the Untapped potential of Fruit tree Wild Diversity for Sustainable Agriculture

The project

Crop Wild Relatives (CWR) are wild plant species closely related to cultivated species. They hold important potential as a source of genetic diversity, offering agronomic and nutritional traits like pest and disease resistance, tolerance to drought, and adaptability to fluctuating climatic conditions affecting fruit quality and production. Harnessing this genetic diversity is crucial for enhancing crop improvement, ensuring sustainable agricultural practices, tackling climate challenges and meeting the demands of food security and better nutrition.

This approach aligns with the goals of the European Green Deal, and the Biodiversity and Farm to Fork strategies, aiming i.a. to reduce pesticide use and risks. Moreover, fruit trees' long lifespan and a current production dominated by only few cultivars make them particularly vulnerable to the effects of global changes. Further research and conservation efforts are thus needed to unlock the full potential of fruit tree CWRs and secure our agricultural future.

Objectives and scope

FruitDiv focuses on stone (Prunus) and pome (Malus and Pyrus) fruit species of the Rosaceae family because of their importance in human nutrition and the transition to sustainable food systems, including balanced diets and low-input agricultural production.

The FruitDiv project aims to:

- Monitor CWR in the European genebanks among the European historical hotspots of diversity;
- Characterise genetically CWR to establish ex situ collections representative of the CWR diversity to be further multiplied in common gardens, and to identify key CWR natural populations to be preserved in situ;
- Share and develop new and high-throughput phenotyping tools and protocols for the evaluation of traits linked to resistance to pests and diseases, and adaptation to low-input cultivation systems in highly contrasted environments;
- Integrate CWRs in plant genetic resources collections and breeding programs by developing new methods for wild-to-crop translational research;
- Promote sustainable data sharing by standardising and giving access to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) genotypic and phenotypic Open Data;
- Develop pre-breeding material and CWR-adapted methodologies for breeding at single and multi-trait scales, making use of existing or future multi-site experimental designs and predictive models;
- Foster a more efficient and sustainable conservation of CWR, in situ, on-farm and through NGOs, and enhance stakeholders' awareness of the value and importance of CWR;
- Promote the use of CWR or first-generation pre-breeding material by breeders to disseminate plant material of interest for growers, organic farmers and the fruit tree industry.

Ambitions and activities

For a species-wide inventory of fruit tree CWR diversity, FruitDiv seeks to

- improve the situation for pome and stone fruit CWR at the European level. As a first step, the project aims to monitor the genetic and phenotypic diversity still available in fruit tree CWR species, including Mediterranean hotspots of biodiversity.

- balance the representativeness of European CWRs in national and European PGR programmes and to enhance their characterisation, thus fostering a better conservation and use.

For a participatory management of CWR with a focus on European biodiversity, FruitDiv aims to

- bring back the management and conservation of CWR in to the spotlight by linking botanists, ecologists, geneticists, breeders, forestry officers, amateur/citizen associations, NGOs and end-users.

- through a multi-actor approach, help implementing a more rational and extensive characterisation of CWR, contributing to its conservation in-situ, ex-situ and on-farm.

- For a better characterisation of CWR diversity that relies on the most innovative technologies, the project strives to

- organise European-wide CWR collections that will be planted in multi-sites and interconnected so as to share genetic and phenotypic characterisation of CWR behaviours in multiple environments and under complementary cultivation regimes using innovative methodologies.

- address the potential interest of long-term maintenance of the same plant material in different agronomic and pedo-climatic conditions across Europe and will propose in the medium-term rationalised conservation strategies, both ex-situ and in-situ, for future uses.

- For a greater insight into the characteristics and the value of fruit tree CWR, FruitDiv will

- develop an innovative strategy relying on germplasm characterisation and implementation of up-to-date methodologies of pangenomic-assisted breeding, graph-based integration of heterogeneous data including biochemical process knowledge and CWR-adapted genomic/metabolomic prediction models.

- use state of the art genomic and phenomic approaches currently under development in major annual crops to fruit tree breeding to drive the sustainable conservation and use of CWR genetic resources.

Consortium

INRAE - INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE POUR L'AGRICULTURE, L'ALIMENTATION ET L'ENVIRONNEMENT	France (Coordinator)	GIS - GOZDARSKI INSTITUT SLOVENIJE	Slovenia
ARCADIA - ARCADIA INTERNATIONAL GEIE	Belgium	GRAB - GROUPE DE RECHERCHE EN AGRICULTUREBIOLOGIQUE ASSOCIATION	France
ARCHE NOAH - ARCHE NOAH GESELLSCHAFT FÜR DIE ERHALTUNG DER KULTURPFLANZENVIelfALT UND IHRE ENTWICKLUNG VEREIN	Austria	IT - INRAE TRANSFERT SAS	France
AUTH - ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	Greece	ILFE - INSTITUT ZA NIZUSKO SUMARSTVO I ZIVOTNU SREDINU	Serbia
BIFSD - BALKANSKA FONDACIJA ZA ODZILIV RAZVOJU	Republic of North Macedonia	IBMASRA - INSTITUTE OF BOTANY AFTER A. TAKHTAJYAN OF NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF REPUBLIC OF ARMENIA	Armenia
CRAG - CENTRE DE RECERCA EN AGRIGENOMICA CSIC-IRTA-LIABUB	Spain	IBRC - INSTITUTUL DE CERETARI BIOLOGICE CLUJ FILIALA A INCDSB BUCURESTI	Romania
CNRS - CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	France	JKI - JULIUS KÜHN-INSTITUT BUNDESFORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FÜR KULTURPFLANZEN	Germany
CRA-W - CENTRE WALLON DE RECHERCHES AGRONOMIQUES	Belgium	NIB - NACIONALNI INSTITUT ZA BIOLOGIJO	Slovenia
CITA - CENTRO DE INVESTIGACION Y TECNOLOGIA AGRICULTURARIA DE ARAGO	Spain	SEAE - SOCIEDAD ESPANOLA DE AGRICULTURA ECOLOGICA	Spain
CEP INNOVATION - CEP INNOVATION SARL	France	UNIBAS - UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DELLA BASILICATA	Italy
ELGO-DIMITRA - ELLINIKOS GEORGIKOS ORGANISMOS - DIMITRA	Greece	UNSA - UNIVERZITET U SARAJEVU	Bosnia and Herzegovina
FEDERPARCII - FEDERAZIONE ITALIANA PARCII E RISERVE NATURALI	Italy	UUI - UPPSALA UNIVERSITET	Sweden
FEM - FONDAZIONE EDMUND MACH	Italy	SFS - ZAVOD ZA GOZDOVE SLOVENIJE	Slovenia
		ACWS - ZVEZA KMETIC SLOVENIJE	Slovenia

 www.he-fruitdiv.eu

Newsletters

Newsletters will be used to inform key stakeholders about the project's progress and results. Publications, events and activities that have taken place in previous months will be included, as well as relevant resources, links and in-depth information. Starting from M12, newsletters will be published biennially during the project and widely distributed. The newsletter will be sent out using a mailing list built on the wide stakeholder mapping and Stakeholder Platform and will also be available on the project website. The newsletter will be developed and sent out via a professional emailing solution (Mailjet). This tool also produces useful analytics and has easy-to-use mailing list management functions.

Practice abstracts

25-30 practice abstracts will be drafted using the EIP-AGRI format and published in English. The target audience for these practice abstracts will be the practitioners. The practice abstracts will be submitted in three sets in M18, M30 and M60 and will be widely distributed e.g. through the EIP-AGRI website² and three deliverables (D7.6, 7.7 and 7.8). The focus of the practice abstracts will be the FRUITDIV innovations resulting from the project. Where relevant, consortium partners may translate the practice abstracts to other languages of their choice.

Policy briefs

Policy briefs will be produced targeting i) EC officers related to research and innovation, sciences, and policymakers; ii) national officers; and iii) regional officers/local authorities.

Press and news releases

Press and news releases will cover different specific issues and channels, in order to draw the stakeholders' and the public's attention towards the project. Press releases will be made before major events and sent to relevant media and will be used to communicate the project key milestones, trainings, events and any other initiatives which are worth bringing up to a selected audience. News releases, on the other hand, have an informal structure of posts, are published on the website, and easily read by the public.

Existing networks and channels for communication will be used to maximise the impact and share FRUITDIV's vision and results, for example through the EU-FarmBook project, blogs related to food systems and data economy, magazines and traditional media. In this context press and news releases will be an important tool.

Blog

Discussion groups in the form of sub-blogs fostering interaction and awareness raising across WPs will take place. Regular blog posts will be published and will be made available through the website.

Scientific publications

FRUITDIV will contribute to sustainable agriculture through the publication of scientific articles. Publications will range from scientific papers to articles in technical reviews. News about the release of scientific and peer-reviewed publications will be shared via the website and social media channels. Research papers will all be published as open access publications.

² EIP-AGRI website, <http://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/content/eip-agri-common-format>

All publications resulting from the project will include a statement informing about the funding source, e.g. “this study was supported by the FRUITDIV project funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe framework programme under grant agreement no 101133964”.

4 Exploitation of results

FRUITDIV strives to share results and outputs of the project open access and free of charge. The dissemination and communication activities of the project will ensure to reach a wide range of farmers, advisors and extension services, policy makers at regional, national and EU level, supply chain actors and retailers, the scientific community, teachers and students and civil society. Such activities throughout the project will enable a strong uptake and exploitation of results towards the end of the project, and after the project’s end.

4.1 Overall strategy

The FRUITDIV research and innovation activities will result in multiple tools addressing CWR management and use. Results of the project will be used for the improvement of crop production systems aiming for a reduction of dependency on pesticide use and climate change adaptation and mitigation.

At an early stage of the project (first year), WP7 will work with each partner to identify the exploitation plans and assess knowledge/capacity gaps or other elements that may prevent exploitation of certain results. This will be done through a questionnaire sent out to all partners, with short follow-up meetings as needed. Based on the answers received by the partners, a detailed plan will be prepared. A centralised, early planning of exploitation activities is considered to greatly enhance the impact achieved. This task will result in a detailed exploitation plan that will enrich this deliverable in the revised version due M60.

4.2 Exploitation routes

Exploitation routes to be explored for some of the foreseen exploitable results and assets will be defined when the first results/outputs of the project start to become visible. Such identification will probably be initiated during the second annual meeting (M24 if we do not count the KoM).

The main research results and assets of FRUITDIV are expected to have a high exploitation potential. The overview below shows assets/results and the exploitation plan per target group. This plan will be further developed in the coming months based on the questionnaire to be sent out to all partners as mentioned in the previous section.

One Innovation Management Committee (IMC) to screen exploitable results of the project and propose to results owners’ potential exploitation ways will be established for working on the exploitation roadmap.

5 Plan of action and performance measures

5.1 Performance measures

Measuring performance of communication and dissemination activities is of high importance and will include monitoring visitor traffic to the website, as well as visitors, followers and interactions on social media, uptake in press or media, number of participants at events/demonstration days and training sessions, number of publications, number of external contact requests, and number of stakeholders receiving the project newsletter.

Each consortium partner will be asked to report regularly to WP7 on communication activities carried out and give feedback on (i) targeted measures to promote the activity, (ii) target audience and number of participants, (iii) key messages formulated for each target group, (iv) what lessons have been learnt and/or what could be improved.

In addition, dissemination activities will also be collected on a regular based (every three months) based on a process that been defined together with the management body of the project and that is presented in the figure below.

Figure 6: Process for collecting communication activities, dissemination activities and publications from consortium partners

Templates have been developed and loaded in the project SharePoint in order for consortium partners to load their information. The process presented above is also relevant to collect information on publications.

Presentations, videos, flyers, brochures and other materials developed and used will be presented on the FRUITDIV website and shared among partners.

5.2 Plan of action

The table below outlines a plan of action related to dissemination activities and communication activities and provides information about the actions planned as well as performance indicators.

Table 2: Plan of action as regards dissemination activities

Dissemination activities and their description		
Activity	Description (Including Dissemination Performance indicators)	
The establishment of the stakeholder platform	The SHP is the main dissemination activities of the project to actors. It will consist of a large list of contacts managed by the WP7 leader that will be used to disseminate information and invite actors to participate to stakeholder engagement events.	1 SHP, 12,000 actors reached
The establishment of the FRUITDIV Editorial Committee	It will play an important role in providing strategic views to maximise interaction with relevant target actors and determine where best to transfer project results and how actors can apply them.	1 FEC meeting, at least, every 6 months
Scientific publications and conferences	Scientific findings will be shared within the scientific communities and multi-disciplinary approaches will be deployed through research papers published in high impact peer-reviewed journals. Results will be presented in meetings and congresses in which specific sessions will be coordinated to increase the project's visibility. Research papers will be published as open access publications.	About 10 scientific papers, and 3 workshops with 100 researchers
Organisation of specific conferences for actors at national level	Conferences will be organised for actors in national languages to communicate and transfer FRUITDIV results down to citizens and consumers.	6 workshops
Project workshops and events	They will be organised to disseminate and exploit results for mutual learning and understanding.	6 capacity building events (300 participants)
Consortium networks and interactions with sister's projects	Project results and outcomes will be disseminated in events by key stakeholder networks of the project partners.	At least 3 running projects
Generic activities	To disseminate key results and outcomes of FRUITDIV (see Section 2.2.1.2)	All the above
Policy briefs	We will target i) EC officers related to research and innovation, sciences, and policy makers; ii) national authorities and public bodies; and iii) regional and local authorities.	5 policy briefs or more

Table 3: Plan of action as regards communication activities

Communication activities and their description		
Activity	Target groups and objectives (Including Communication Performance indicators)	
Public website	All	Unique visitors' views by 15,000 . Links to up to 27 partners' websites as well as links to up to 20 other EU projects and initiatives.
Digital newsletters	All	Released >8
Social media	All	3 social media channels, audience >1000 ; posts >100 (source social media insights)

Communication activities and their description		
Targeted and easily accessible end-user material	All	Practice abstracts >40, published videos >5 (source: digital distribution channel insights)
Branding & material	All	1 visual identity, 1 flyer, >5 fact sheets (Source: partners' regular reporting)
Multipliers	All, focus on advisors and policymakers	Press release >5, interviews > 5
Final conference	All	1 event

5.3 Long-term sustainability and dissemination of projects results

The dissemination and engagement activities that are part of FRUITDIV aim to create a long-term sustainability ecosystem through regular collaborations and relationships among consortium partners and stakeholders will keep going also after the end of the project.

Furthermore, the project sets out to take advantage of the stakeholder networks contacted during the project which will facilitate and support the continuous communication and dissemination among relevant groups after the completion of projects. In addition, the FRUITDIV project website will be result-oriented towards the end of the project (compared to the project-centred approach at the beginning of the project) and will therefore be an interesting tool for end users. The project website will remain in place for at least five (5) years after the completion of the project to enable other stakeholders to build on FRUITDIV tools for future research.

6 Management of communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities

6.1 Tasks and responsibilities

ARCADIA is the WP7 leader and is thus responsible for the development and execution of the overall communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy of FRUITDIV, and most of the related activities. However, the work of WP7 is highly dependent on the input from all other work packages and partners as regards their separate activities, progress and results in order to provide a basis for content to communicate and disseminate. Furthermore, some of the partners are assigned as leaders for certain tasks and responsibilities within WP7, and some work packages are particularly connected to communication and dissemination activities (e.g. WP1 to WP6).

The table below outlines the main roles and responsibilities.

Table 4: Roles and responsibilities

Partner	Responsibility and involvement
INRAE (project coordinator)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> As project coordinator, INRAE is the primary interlocutor of ARCADIA on communication and dissemination activities and will be asked to validate the proposed dissemination, communication and exploitation plan.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INRAE will provide feedback and approval on communication and dissemination contents to be released on behalf of FRUITDIV (where needed/requested).
ARCADIA (WP7 leader)	<p>WP7 leader for communication, dissemination and exploitation activities, as well as task leader for all tasks under this work package excluding Task 7.3, 7.5 and 7.6</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing, updating and implementing the present dissemination, communication and exploitation plan. • Defining key messages that will convey the objectives and goals of the project based on the perspectives of the project's target audience. • Developing FRUITDIV logo, visual identity and various communication materials, e.g. leaflet, poster, newsletter. • Internal point of contact for all communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities that will take place on behalf of FRUITDIV. • Designing, updating and maintaining of the project website and social media profiles. • Producing content to be published on the website and external channels, newsletters and social media platforms, based on the active contribution of all partners. • Monitoring the impact and measuring performance of communication material and activities.
All consortium partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reviewing and validating the present dissemination, communication and exploitation plan. • Assisting ARCADIA by providing input needed to create the FRUITDIV communication materials. • Sharing project information on their website, social media pages and newsletters. All their online tools should link to the FRUITDIV website and social media pages. • Keeping ARCADIA informed as to relevant progress made by the project in their respective work packages, and any related communication activities and efforts, as well as information collected about their impact (incl. events, publications, news). • Assistance on drafting the EIP-AGRI practice abstracts as required. • Boosting presence of FRUITDIV on social media. • All partners will promote the project to their own contacts and invite them to subscribe to the newsletter via the subscription form on the FRUITDIV website.

6.2 Editorial committee

A FRUITDIV Editorial Committee has been put in place to ensure quality and clarity of the various communication and dissemination tools of the project. While such committee is not consulted regarding each and every document (news, website), a consultation is organised where needed and in particular for certain key communication tools that are produced to last throughout the project (e.g. concept note, general presentation of the project, leaflet and poster).

The Committee is made up of members of the management committee, the WP leaders and other members on a voluntary basis. It is consulted mainly via email. Generally, WP7 initiates the process by sharing a semi-final document/tool, asking for feedback from the members of the Committee. Once feedback has been received by all, comments are taken into consideration by WP7, and the document/tool is revised as needed and finalised. In cases where required, the Editorial Committee may organise a meeting to discuss a specific tool/deliverable. Members of the Committee may also request to provide input on certain tools/documents, even in cases where this has not been initiated by WP7.

7 Data protection and open science

7.1 Data protection

FRUITDIV ensures that personal data processing and management comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) provisions.

For users from the EU viewing the website, a cookie banner will be displayed, providing a cookie policy and acquiring consent for the installation of cookies.

7.2 Open science

Within the FRUITDIV project, principles of the Horizon Europe Open Science will be implemented, referring to the scientific process based on cooperative work, tools and the diffusion of knowledge. All FRUITDIV partners will follow methods and steps that assure the early and open sharing of the project outcomes. More specifically, pre-registrations of the research plans of the study implementation, as well as registered reports will be submitted to Open Access Repositories.

FRUITDIV will manage research data and other research outputs responsibly, following the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) principles, using a Data Management Plan and providing open access to research data via a trusted repository under the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”.

For further details about Open Science and FRUITDIV’s efforts to increase data re-use, please consult deliverables 7.2, D7.3 and D7.3: Data Management Plan.

8 Conclusions

This initial DEC strategy, including a detailed plan will be implemented as of M4 of the project. A final version of the DEC plan will be drafted and submitted M48 of the project. The Data Management Plans are published in complementary deliverables (D7.2, D7.3 and D7.4).